

M UNIVERSITY OF
MICHIGAN

Popular Financing Report

Authors:

Attivor Novisi (1027132)

Annovati Chiara (958102)

Gill Navraaj Kaur (1027455)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

02

GENERAL DATA

04

MISSION & VISION

05

RANKINGS

06

DEMOGRAPHICS

11

BOARD OF REGENTS

12

UNIVERSITY GOVERNANCE &
COMMUNITY

15

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

27

MAJOR POLICIES

29

DISSEMINATION PLAN

31

THE SIX CAPITAL

40

PAPER METHODOLOGY

General Data

The University of Michigan is the oldest higher-educational institution in the state, and among the earliest research universities in the nation; it was founded in 1817, twenty years before the Michigan Territory achieved statehood

More than any other university, UOM has the potential to be so much more than the sum of its many excellent parts. It's this potential to have a positive impact on the society the university serves that represents its greatest value. Here are a few facts and figures that help illustrate the successes of UOM.

FREE TUITION
for families with incomes
\$75000 and under assets
below

1 out of 4 in state
undergraduates
pay no tuition
due to financial
aid

THE UNIVERSITY OF MICHIGAN (ANN ARBOR, DEARBORN, FLINT CAMPUSES)

IN 2021, MICHIGAN STUDENTS CAME FROM

83
All Michigan
countries

50
states

135
countries

Research

- #2 in research volume among U.S. research universities
- \$973M in Annual Federally Sponsored Research (2022)
- 1,500+ Students participated in the Undergraduate Research Opportunity Program (2020)
- \$1.71B Research expenditures (2022)

Innovation Partnership

- 433 new inventions reported (2022)
- 16 New business startups (2022)

Affordability

- 2 of 3 first-year students receive financial aid
- More than \$754.6M in scholarships and fellowships awarded to students (2020-21)
- Money Magazine ranks U-M No. 1 for value (2022)

2022 entering class

- 3.9-4.0 Average High School GPA
- 31–34 Average ACT
- 1350-1530 Average SAT range

M athletics

- 411 All-time Big 10 athletic championships
- 900+ Student-athletes
- 29 NCAA Division I teams

Academics

- 110 Grad programs in the top 10 — U.S. News & World Report (2022)
- 97% first-year student retention rate
- 93% of students graduate within six years
- 19 Schools and colleges
- 275+ Degree programs
- 15:1 Student to faculty ratio

VISION

Engaging minds, preparing leaders through academic excellence, student centeredness and engaged citizenship.

MISSION

The mission of the University of Michigan is to serve the people of Michigan and the world through preeminence in creating, communicating, preserving and applying knowledge, art, and academic values, and in developing leaders and citizens who will challenge the present and enrich the future.

Rankings

The University of Michigan is once again the No. 23 university in the world and the No. 14 university in the United States, according to the latest Times Higher Education World University Rankings.

ANN ARBOR CAMPUS

#3

**National
undergraduate
public universities**

#1

**U.S. Public
University**

#1

**Best small college
towns in America**

#18

**World reputation
ranking**

The University of Michigan, near Detroit, offers a vibrant college town experience. Freshmen have guaranteed housing but aren't required to live on campus. With 1,500+ student organizations and strong athletic traditions, including a fierce football rivalry with Ohio State, there's a rich campus life. Michigan also boasts top graduate programs like Ross School of Business, College of Engineering, Law School, and Medical School, along with renowned schools like Dentistry and Taubman College for Architecture. The University of Michigan Hospitals and Health Centers are among the nation's best.

Student Population

	TOTAL	UNDERGRADUATE	GRADUATE
2023 POPULATION	51,225	32,695	18,530
2022 POPULATION	50,278	32,282	17,996
Men	24,655	15,767	8,888
Women	25,623	16,515	9,108

Degree programs

Undergraduate

Graduate

RACE/ETHNICITY

This section analyzes the student population by race/ethnicity at University of Michigan-Ann Arbor. There are 83 American Indian/Native American, 24,858 White, 2,144 Black/African American, 7,350 Asian, 3,549 Hispanic, 21 Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander, and 2,164 students with other races.

STUDENT AGE DISTRIBUTION

The following table and chart show the student enrollment by age distribution at University of Michigan-Ann Arbor.

Under 18	963	3
Age 18-19	14043	8
Age 20-21	14457	574
Age 22-24	2250	6441
Age 25-29	386	7072
Age 30-34	107	2516
Age 35-39	38	767
Age 40-49	23	477
Age 50-64	11	129
Over 64	4	9
Age Un-Known	0	0

Employees Demographics

Number of Employees:

35,000 employees

Gender:

MEN
47%

WOMEN
53%

What is the average age of university of Michigan employees?

- The most common age range of University of Michigan employees is 20-30 years. 49% of University of Michigan employees are between the ages of 20-30 years.
- The least common age range of University of Michigan employees is less than 18 years. 4% of University of Michigan employees are between the ages of less than 18 years.

What is the average length of employment at university of Michigan?

- A plurality of employees at University of Michigan stay for 1-2 years. 28% of University of Michigan employees stay at the company for 1-2 years.
- It's rare for an employee to stay with University of Michigan for 8-10 years. Only 6% of University of Michigan employees stay at the company for 8-10 years.

University of Michigan salary range

- A plurality of employees at University of Michigan earns \$40k-60k. 44% of employees earn a salary of \$40k-60k a year.
- The least common salary at University of Michigan is >\$200k. Only 1% of University of Michigan employees earn a salary of >\$200k a year.

SALARY RANGE	UNIVERSITY OF MICHIGAN
<\$25k	330 jobs
\$25k-40k	2,404 jobs
\$40k-60k	7,204 jobs
\$60k-100k	4,843 jobs
\$100k-200k	1,485 jobs
>\$200k	145 jobs

University of Michigan employees education

- The most common highest degree level of University of Michigan employees is bachelors, with 64% of employees having at least a bachelors.
- The most common major among University of Michigan employees is psychology. 10% of University of Michigan employees majored in psychology.

Degrees of University of Michigan Employees

Majors Of University Of Michigan Employees

Board of Regents

The University operates under the governance of the Board of Regents, consisting of eight members elected statewide every two years. The University president is an ex officio member of the board. These Regents serve without pay for overlapping eight-year terms, as mandated by the Michigan Constitution of 1963. They have comprehensive authority, including "general supervision," control, and direction over the institution's funds and expenditures, ensuring effective management and oversight of the University's affairs.

University Governance and Community

The university of Michigan has established processes for IT Governance and Data Governance to guide the technology and data assets of our university.

IT Governance

The IT Council advises the VPIT-CIO (Vice President for Information Technology & Chief Information Officer) across academic and medical campuses, focusing on areas like research, teaching, and security, with input from deans, faculty, IT leaders, and students.

The Strategic Technology Advisory Committee (STAC) guides U-M's tech services, offering strategic advice and enhancing communication within the IT community.

Advisory, Governing, and Sharing Groups amplify the campus voice, shaping improvement priorities and strategic direction across U-M's technology landscape.

Data Governance

Data Governance focuses on managing, protecting, and classifying university data as one of its most important institutional assets. It helps ensure that there is appropriate accountability for maintaining data quality and integrity.

For the Michigan IT Community

More than 2,600 IT professionals work in U-M's schools and colleges, libraries, research institutes, health system, technology offices, and administrative units to further the university's missions through the innovative use of technology.

The Office of the VPIT-CIO sponsors multiple programs to build community, foster skills & professional development, and promote innovation across U-M's IT professionals

Tech Showcase & Social

The Tech Showcase & Social event introduces cutting-edge university technologies, fostering community bonds through various activities. Its aim is to nurture curiosity, cooperation, and unity, promoting a connected and innovative learning environment.

Communities of Practice

The Michigan IT working group facilitates Communities of Practice (CoPs) where professionals with similar interests exchange information and ideas about specific IT topics, aligning with the university's missions.

Mentor Program

U-M IT staff have the opportunity to participate as mentors or mentees in this program, fostering expanded professional networks, knowledge sharing, and progress towards individual development objectives.

Consolidated Financial Statement

The University's financial report contains essential statements such as the

- Consolidated Statement of Net Position,
- the Consolidated Statement of Revenues, Expenses, and Changes in Net Position,
- the Consolidated Statement of Cash Flows,
- the Statement of Fiduciary Net Position,
- and the Statement of Changes in Fiduciary Net Position.

These foundational financial documents adhere to GASB principles, which define the standards for external financial reporting in public colleges and universities. Within these statements, the University's business-type activities are detailed in the consolidated financial documents, whereas its fiduciary activities are outlined in the fiduciary financial statements.

Revenue distribution

(in millions)	2022	2021
Operating revenues:		
Net student tuition and fees	\$ 1,586.1	\$ 1,480.8
Sponsored programs	1,361.3	1,264.4
Patient care revenues, net	5,605.7	5,351.1
Other	507.1	308.0
	9,060.2	8,404.3
Operating expenses	10,548.4	9,520.0
Operating loss	(1,488.2)	(1,115.7)
Nonoperating and other revenues (expenses):		
State educational appropriations	391.6	373.2
Federal Pell grants	53.6	53.4
Federal economic relief funds	151.9	255.7
Private gifts for operating activities	219.1	184.1
Net investment income	336.3	5,141.3
Interest expense	(125.2)	(97.9)
Federal subsidies for interest on Build America Bonds	5.5	5.5
State capital appropriations	29.8	32.1
Endowment and capital gifts and grants	235.0	151.0
Other	(14.0)	(6.6)
Nonoperating and other revenues, net	1,283.6	6,091.8
(Decrease) increase in net position	(204.6)	4,976.1
Net position, beginning of year	19,503.1	14,527.0
Net position, end of year	\$ 19,298.5	\$ 19,503.1

Extraordinary transfers

Federal economic relief funds represent amounts received from various government agencies to provide economic assistance to entities that have been negatively impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic.

For the years ended June 30, federal economic relief funds are summarized as follows:

For the years ended June 30, patient care revenues by source are summarized as follows:

(in millions)	2022	2021	2020
University of Michigan Health	\$ 4,926.4	\$ 4,682.6	\$ 4,152.6
UM Health	522.4	507.0	464.3
Michigan Health Corporation	22.6	30.9	36.4
Other	134.3	130.6	114.6
	<u>\$ 5,605.7</u>	<u>\$ 5,351.1</u>	<u>\$ 4,767.9</u>

Alternative assets, notably venture capital and private equity, yielded strong returns of 78% and 51%, while equities led the marketable assets class with a 51% return. State capital funds facilitated key renovations in academic buildings, including the W.K. Kellogg Institute and Dental Building in Ann Arbor, Engineering Lab Building in Dearborn, and William R. Murchie Science Building in Flint.

Sustaining excellence, the University received significant private gifts: \$189 million for endowment and \$46 million for capital initiatives in 2022, compared to \$136 million and \$15 million in 2021, respectively.

Major donations supported diverse initiatives such as the health system, Ross School of Business, and Intercollegiate Athletics.

To address financial challenges, the University prioritizes ongoing cost containment, focusing on compensation, benefits, energy, technology, and facility maintenance, which constitute 62% of total expenses.

(in millions)	2022	2021	2020
Provider Relief Fund	\$ 18.7	\$ 135.3	\$ 134.7
Higher Education Emergency Relief Fund	110.3	77.1	9.1
Coronavirus State and Local Fiscal Recovery Fund	16.7		
Coronavirus Relief Fund		42.4	
Other	6.2	0.9	
	<u>\$ 151.9</u>	<u>\$ 255.7</u>	<u>\$ 143.8</u>

Investment distribution

The University's long-term investment strategy combined with its endowment spending policy serves to insulate operations from expected volatility in the capital markets and provides for a stable and predictable level of spending distributions from the endowment.

The success of the University's longterm investment strategy is evidenced by strong returns over sustained periods of time and the ability to limit losses in the face of challenging markets.

The composition of the University's endowment, life income and other investments at June 30 is summarized as follows:

(in millions)	2022	2021
Endowment investments	\$ 17,347	\$ 17,023
Life income investments	178	191
Noncurrent portion of insurance and benefits obligations investments	291	293
Other	22	26
	\$ 17,838	\$ 17,533

The University's endowment funds consist of both permanent endowments and funds functioning as endowment. Permanent endowments are those funds received from donors with the stipulation that the principal remain intact and be invested in perpetuity to produce income that is to be expended for the purposes specified by the donors.

Funds functioning as endowment consist of restricted gifts or unrestricted funds that have been allocated by the University for long-term investment purposes, but are not limited by donor stipulations requiring the University to preserve principal in perpetuity.

Programs supported by endowment funds include scholarships, fellowships, professorships, research efforts and other important programs and activities.

Budget

The University of Michigan-Ann Arbor (U-M) advances its highest priorities for the FY 2024 budget, including affordability, access, and success for students; academic excellence through investments in faculty and research; and support for our staff and administrative infrastructure. The FY 2024 budget proposal provides a balanced budget amidst significant cost pressures while maintaining the resources necessary to realize ongoing excellence during an era of bold change

The FY 2024 BUDGET PROPOSAL PRIORITIZES:

Students: Affordability, Access, Success	Students: Affordability, Access, Success	Students: Affordability, Access, Success
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expands eligibility for the Go Blue Guarantee Increasing the entering undergraduate class Invests in mental health & wellness programs Provides summer academic support for doctoral students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovation in biointerfaces, precision health, quantum computing, digital studies Investment in research cores and infrastructure Numerous faculty recruitment and retention programs across schools and colleges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provides merit program and professional development funding Investments in technology to improve service and efficiency Expands talent acquisition program

Campus Level Budget & Trends

<i>in millions</i>	FY 2019 Actual	FY 2020 Actual	FY 2021 Actual	FY 2022 Actual	FY 2023 Budget	FY 2024 Budget*
REVENUE:						
Ann Arbor Campus	\$ 4,232	\$ 4,422	\$ 4,399	\$ 4,784	\$ 4,829	\$ 5,282
Michigan Medicine	5,009	5,105	5,683	5,858	6,161	7,769
Dearborn Campus	184	188	197	209	192	198
Flint Campus	142	139	161	153	142	140
Total Revenue:	\$ 9,567	\$ 9,854	\$ 10,440	\$ 11,004	\$ 11,323	\$ 13,389
EXPENDITURES:						
Ann Arbor Campus	\$ 4,094	\$ 4,229	\$ 4,135	\$ 4,324	\$ 4,816	\$ 5,087
Michigan Medicine	4,969	5,264	5,358	5,842	5,082	7,662
Dearborn Campus	183	186	174	204	192	198
Flint Campus	146	139	122	152	142	140
Total Expenditures:	\$ 9,391	\$ 9,818	\$ 9,789	\$ 10,521	\$ 11,232	\$ 13,087
OPERATING FUND MARGIN:						
Ann Arbor Campus	\$ 138	\$ 193	\$ 264	\$ 460	\$ 13	\$ 195
Michigan Medicine	40	(160)	325	16	79	107
Dearborn Campus	2	1	24	5	-	-
Flint Campus	(4)	1	40	2	-	-
Operating Fund Margin:	\$ 176	\$ 35	\$ 652	\$ 483	\$ 92	\$ 302

*Includes Sparrow Health System

Public debt

The University utilizes commercial paper, backed by a general revenue pledge, to provide interim financing for its capital improvement program.

Outstanding commercial paper is converted to long-term debt financing as appropriate, within the normal course of business. Outstanding bonds are also supported by the University's general revenue pledge.

During 2022, the University issued \$2,469 million of general revenue bonds with a net original issue premium of \$14 million, which included \$2,413 million of fixed rate, taxable bonds, and \$56 million of fixed rate, tax-exempt bonds. Total bond proceeds of \$2,483 million were utilized to refund \$69 million of existing bonds, establish an escrow of \$412 million to advance refund existing bonds, as well as provide \$299 million for capital projects designed to advance the University's commitment to decarbonization, \$1,686 million for capital projects and general purposes, and \$17 million for debt issuance costs.

The composition of the University's debt at June 30 is summarized as follows:

(in millions)	2022	2021
Variable rate:		
Commercial paper	\$ 141	\$ 154
Bonds	426	523
Fixed rate bonds	4,639	2,637
	\$ 5,206	\$ 3,314

Diversification in revenue stream

One of the University’s greatest strengths is the diverse streams of revenue that supplement its student tuition and fees, including private support from individuals, foundations and corporations, along with government and other sponsored programs, state appropriations and investment income. The University continues to aggressively seek funding from all possible sources consistent with its mission in order to supplement student tuition and prudently manage the financial resources realized from these efforts to fund its operating activities, which include instruction, patient care and research. The following is a graphic illustration of revenues by source, both operating and nonoperating, which are used to fund the University’s operating activities for the year ended June 30, 2022 (amounts are presented in millions of dollars). Revenues from Health System and other clinical services totalling \$5,606million continues to be the largest source of operating revenue for the university of michigan .

Funding from the state of Michigan continues to be an essential source of financial support for U-M. In FY 2022, state educational appropriations totaled \$392 million. The university is very appreciative of the ongoing support of higher education and U-M by residents of the state, particularly in a year that saw inflation and ongoing economic issues due to the COVID-19 pandemic. U-M’s operating budget continues to balance academic excellence and investment in the future with student affordability and access. Certain recurring sources of the University’s revenues are considered nonoperating, as defined by GASB, such as state appropriations, distributions from investments, private gifts and federal Pell grants

Michigan Medicine Continues To Be a Leader In Health Care

Michigan Medicine — which includes University of Michigan Health (UMH), University of Michigan Medical School, Michigan Health Corporation and UMHealth — is acknowledged across the country as a leader in advanced patient care, innovative research to improve human health and comprehensive education of physicians and medical scientists. Despite challenges from the COVID-19 omicron surge, supply chain issues and workforce shortages, UMH realized positive financial results in FY 2022, with a 1.9 percent — or \$94 million — operating margin on operating revenues of \$5.0 billion.

UMH also recognized federal pandemic relief funding of \$30 million.

Dedication, talent and commitment to the highest standards of patient care along with a focus on inclusion and teamwork enabled Michigan Medicine to successfully manage ongoing COVID-19 issues and introduce new initiatives to improve access. These initiatives include the Care at Home program, which offers patients hospital-level care combined with the opportunity to recover at home.

This program provides eligible patients with the option to receive nurse and physician visits — plus a wide array of tests, treatments and monitoring — in their homes. That allows some hospitalized patients to return home sooner to receive care in familiar surroundings, closer to loved ones.

Consolidated financial statement of net position

The consolidated statement of net position presents the financial position of the University at the end of the fiscal year and includes all assets, deferred outflows, liabilities and deferred inflows of the University. The difference between total assets and deferred outflows as compared to total liabilities and deferred inflows – net position – is one indicator of the current financial condition of the University, while the change in net position is an indication of whether the overall financial condition has improved or worsened during the year.

The University's assets, deferred outflows, liabilities, deferred inflows and net position at June 30 are as follows:

(in thousands)	June 30,	
	2022	2021
Assets		
Current Assets:		
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 2,951,905	\$ 1,003,846
Investments for operating activities	1,691,019	1,912,859
Investments for capital activities	559,411	627,926
Investments for student loan activities	68,387	70,481
Accounts receivable, net	996,475	970,600
Current portion of notes and pledges receivable, net	108,164	108,789
Current portion of other assets	179,403	183,656
Cash collateral held by agent	23,037	20,040
Total Current Assets	6,577,801	4,898,197
Noncurrent Assets:		
Unexpended bond proceeds	305,452	52,451
Endowment, life income and other investments	17,837,664	17,532,653
Notes and pledges receivable, net	273,986	260,756
Other assets	126,435	131,951
Capital assets, net	6,265,812	6,432,423
Total Noncurrent Assets	24,809,349	24,410,234
Total Assets	31,387,150	29,308,431
Deferred Outflows	1,045,098	1,124,313
(in thousands)	June 30,	
	2022	2021
Liabilities		
Current Liabilities:		
Accounts payable	408,727	356,020
Accrued compensation and other	754,888	746,422
Unearned revenue	412,866	553,784
Current portion of insurance and benefits reserves	646,591	269,789
Current portion of obligations for postemployment benefits	97,354	95,581
Commercial paper and current portion of bonds payable	209,311	235,875
Long-term bonds payable subject to remarketing, net	274,392	300,542
Collateral held for securities lending	23,037	20,040
Total Current Liabilities	2,827,166	2,578,053
Noncurrent Liabilities:		
Accrued compensation	23,496	103,563
Insurance and benefits reserves	177,023	170,059
Obligations for defined benefit pension plan, net	(22,675)	(6,322)
Obligations for postemployment benefits	4,200,305	4,316,565
Obligations under life income agreements	73,554	76,995
Government loan advances	43,580	55,585
Bonds payable	4,722,319	2,777,621
Other liabilities	296,462	382,819
Total Noncurrent Liabilities	9,514,064	7,876,885
Total Liabilities	12,341,230	10,454,938
Deferred Inflows	792,557	474,742
Net Position		
Net investment in capital assets	3,522,018	3,669,608
Restricted:		
Nonexpendable	2,821,876	2,625,459
Expendable	7,615,023	7,582,296
Unrestricted	5,339,544	5,625,701
Total Net Position	\$ 19,298,461	\$ 19,503,064

The statement of net position

The University continues to maintain and protect its strong financial foundation.

This financial health, as reflected in the University’s net position, results from the prudent utilization of financial resources including careful cost controls, preservation of endowment funds, conservative utilization of debt and adherence to a long-range capital plan for the maintenance and replacement of the physical plant. Current assets consist primarily of cash and cash equivalents, operating and capital investments, and accounts receivable and increased \$1.7 billion to \$6.6 billion at June 30, 2022, as compared to \$4.9 billion at June 30, 2021, primarily as a result of the University’s continued focus on liquidity. Cash, cash equivalents and investments for operating activities totaled \$4.6 billion at June 30, 2022, which represents approximately six months of total expenses excluding depreciation. Deferred outflows represent the consumption of net assets attributable to a future period and are primarily associated with the University’s obligations for post employment benefits, debt and derivative activity, and the defined benefit pension plan for UMH-West. Deferred outflows totaled \$1.0 billion and \$1.1 billion at June 30, 2022 and 2021, respectively. Current liabilities consist primarily of accounts payable, accrued compensation, unearned revenue, commercial paper, the current portion of bonds payable and net long-term bonds payable subject to remarketing. Current liabilities totaled \$2.8 billion and \$2.6 billion at June 30, 2022 and 2021, respectively. Deferred inflows represent the acquisition of net assets attributable to a future period and are primarily associated with the University’s obligations for postemployment benefits, the defined benefit pension plan for UMH-West and irrevocable split-interest agreements. Deferred inflows totaled \$793 million and \$475 million at June 30, 2022 and 2021, respectively.

INVESTMENT PERFORMANCE

INVESTMENT PERFORMANCE	RETURN FOR THE 12-MONTH PERIOD ENDED JUNE 30, 2022	ANNUALIZED 5-YEAR RETURN	ANNUALIZED 10-YEAR RETURN
LONG TERM PORTFOLIO	2.1%	11.6%	10.2%
U-M'S BENCHMARK	-3.6%	8.4%	8.4%
BLENDED PASSIVE INDEX	-11.8%	5.8%	7.0%

The Long Term Portfolio’s 10-year, 5-year and 12-month annualized returns exceeded those of its custom U-M Benchmark and Blended Passive Index. The 12-month return of 2.1 percent reflects a volatile year in the financial markets, which were reacting to rising interest rates, high levels of inflation and increased geopolitical risks. With a 10-year annualized return of 10.2 percent, U-M’s Long Term Portfolio is in the top quartile of performance relative to other college and university endowment investment portfolios.

Consolidated statement of revenues, expenses and changes in net position

The consolidated statement of revenues, expenses and changes in net position presents the University's results of operations. In accordance with GASB reporting principles, revenues and expenses are classified as either operating or nonoperating. The University's revenues, expenses and changes in net position for the years ended June 30 are as follows

(in thousands)	2022	2021
Operating Revenues		
Student tuition and fees	\$ 2,085,014	\$ 1,977,983
Less scholarship allowances	498,938	497,162
Net student tuition and fees	1,586,076	1,480,821
Federal grants and contracts	1,095,005	1,019,559
State and local grants and contracts	12,372	12,577
Nongovernmental sponsored programs	253,876	232,286
Sales and services of educational departments	141,498	140,594
Auxiliary enterprises:		
Patient care revenues (net of provision for bad debts of \$146,099 in 2022 and \$140,672 in 2021)	5,605,741	5,351,066
Student residence fees (net of scholarship allowances of \$24,767 in 2022 and \$10,260 in 2021)	121,919	50,334
Other revenues	241,115	115,029
Student loan interest income and fees	2,622	2,057
Total Operating Revenues	9,060,224	8,404,323
Operating Expenses		
Compensation and benefits	6,573,834	6,137,455
Supplies and services	3,137,104	2,562,079
Depreciation	606,523	620,037
Scholarships and fellowships	230,946	200,431
Total Operating Expenses	10,548,407	9,520,002
Operating Loss	(1,488,183)	(1,115,679)
Nonoperating Revenues (Expenses)		
State educational appropriations	391,639	373,230
Federal Pell grants	53,552	53,396
Federal economic relief funds	151,926	255,673
Private gifts for other than capital and endowment purposes	219,068	184,108
Net investment income	336,345	5,141,252
Interest expense	(125,248)	(97,924)
Federal subsidies for interest on Build America Bonds	5,519	5,529
Total Nonoperating Revenues, Net	1,032,801	5,915,264
(Loss) Income Before Other Revenues (Expenses)	(455,382)	4,799,585
Other Revenues (Expenses)		
State capital appropriations	29,760	32,062
Capital gifts and grants	46,222	14,639
Private gifts for permanent endowment purposes	188,803	136,402
Other	(14,006)	(6,624)
Total Other Revenues, Net	250,779	176,479
(Decrease) Increase in Net Position	(204,603)	4,976,064
Net Position, Beginning of Year	19,503,064	14,527,000
Net Position, End of Year	\$ 19,298,461	\$ 19,503,064

Consolidated statement of cash flows

The consolidated statement of cash flows provides additional information about the University's financial results by reporting the major sources and uses of cash. The University's cash flows for the years ended June 30 are summarized as follows:

(in thousands)	Year Ended June 30,	
	2022	2021
Cash Flows from Operating Activities		
Student tuition and fees	\$ 1,590,126	\$ 1,487,613
Federal, state and local grants and contracts	1,110,673	1,016,803
Nongovernmental sponsored programs	266,398	238,827
Sales and services of educational departments and other	391,838	274,661
Patient care revenues	5,367,111	4,994,855
Student residence fees	122,470	50,936
Payments to employees	(4,884,734)	(4,543,478)
Payments for benefits	(1,524,661)	(1,142,841)
Payments to suppliers	(2,688,744)	(2,467,119)
Payments for scholarships and fellowships	(230,946)	(200,431)
Student loans issued	(7,014)	(6,430)
Student loans collected	14,985	15,662
Student loan interest and fees collected	2,622	2,057
Net Cash Used in Operating Activities	(469,876)	(278,885)
Cash Flows from Noncapital Financing Activities		
State educational appropriations	390,943	331,523
Federal Pell grants	53,552	53,396
Federal economic relief funds	149,484	249,737
Private gifts and other receipts	378,153	285,710
Proceeds from issuance of debt	1,700,000	
Interest payments on debt	(18,787)	(16,830)
Payments for bond refunding and related costs	(13,651)	
Student direct lending receipts	312,072	312,147
Student direct lending disbursements	(315,257)	(311,608)
Amounts received for annuity and life income funds	1,223	5,979
Amounts paid to annuitants and life beneficiaries and related expenses	(11,194)	(9,118)
Net Cash Provided by Noncapital Financing Activities	2,626,538	900,936
Cash Flows from Capital and Related Financing Activities		
State capital appropriations	29,491	31,033
Private gifts and other receipts	38,750	37,792
Principal and interest payments on lease liabilities	(67,299)	(66,409)
Proceeds from issuance of capital debt	782,838	164,875
Principal payments on capital debt	(527,900)	(211,690)
Interest payments on capital debt	(119,730)	(86,834)
Federal subsidies for Build America Bonds interest	5,524	5,531
Payments for bond refunding and related costs	(3,104)	
Purchases of capital assets	(428,852)	(498,316)
Proceeds from sales of capital assets	9,214	1,739
Net Cash Used in Capital and Related Financing Activities	(281,068)	(622,279)

(in thousands)	Year Ended June 30,	
	2022	2021
Cash Flows from Investing Activities		
Interest and dividends on investments, net	44,637	24,323
Proceeds from sales and maturities of investments	9,795,835	8,341,799
Purchases of investments	(9,405,226)	(8,710,091)
Net (increase) decrease in unexpended capital debt proceeds	(253,001)	73,454
Net (increase) decrease in cash equivalents from noncurrent investments	(95,546)	8,232
Net increase in fiduciary custodial funds and other	(14,234)	(9,044)
Net Cash Provided by (Used in) Investing Activities	72,465	(271,327)
Net Increase (Decrease) in Cash and Cash Equivalents	1,948,059	(271,555)
Cash and Cash Equivalents, Beginning of Year	1,003,846	1,275,401
Cash and Cash Equivalents, End of Year	\$ 2,951,905	\$ 1,003,846

Reconciliation of Operating Loss to Net Cash Used in Operating Activities:

Operating loss	\$ (1,488,183)	\$ (1,115,679)
Adjustments to reconcile operating loss to net cash used in operating activities:		
Depreciation expense	606,523	620,037
Changes in assets and liabilities:		
Accounts receivable, net	(10,502)	(331,111)
Notes and pledges receivable, net	(416)	(283)
Other assets	9,280	(46,807)
Accounts payable	60,333	(11,484)
Accrued compensation and other	(145,861)	209,818
Unearned revenue	(141,472)	(27,287)
Insurance and benefits reserves	383,766	136,417
Obligations for defined benefit pension plan, net	(16,353)	(5,075)
Obligations for postemployment benefits	(114,487)	934,658
Changes in deferred outflows	105,899	(615,072)
Changes in deferred inflows	281,597	(27,017)
Net Cash Used in Operating Activities	\$ (469,876)	\$ (278,885)

Want to know more about
the University's financial
statements?

Major policies

CAMPUS RESOURCES AND SERVICES

The University of Michigan and the School of Public Health provide a wealth of services that support undergraduate and graduate students in their personal and academic journeys, from cutting-edge library and learning spaces, to financial advising, family assistance, and computing resources.

UOM CAMPUS RESOURCES

There are a number of resources available to students across the University of Michigan campus. Some of the most important include:

- Michigan Center for Interprofessional Education (IPE)
- Michigan Institute for Clinical and Health Research (MICHR)
- Sexual Assault Prevention and Awareness Center (SAPAC)
- University Health Service
- Counseling and Psychological Services (CAPS)
- Veterans, National Guard/Reservists, Active Duty, and Military Family Members
- International Center
- Office of Services for Students with Disabilities (SSD)

Michigan Public Health study spaces

The School of Public Health provides students with abundant study spaces, including private lounges, group areas, and digital signboards for collaborative work. Designated student areas like Room 1627 and the Crossroads lounge, along with public lounges and the JavaBlu Café, offer relaxation and collaboration opportunities. Students can also reserve conference rooms and classrooms for their needs.

The University of Michigan Library system comprises 20 specialized libraries, offering extensive resources to graduate students. With over 11 million volumes, it's one of North America's largest academic libraries, known for its research facilities. Graduate students can borrow materials from all U-M libraries, access inter-library loans, and use document delivery services. The Taubman Health Sciences Library specifically caters to health sciences students, including those from the School of Public Health, making it a popular study spot. Visit the library website for more details on available services for graduate students.

FINANCIAL SERVICES

The university prepares a survey of bank fees and services to assist students with their banking decisions. The cost of attendance for graduate students is based on standard student budgets that the University's Office of Financial Aid (OFA) establishes each year.

Office of Financial Aid

The Office of Financial Aid (OFA) oversees federal, state, and institutional financial aid programs, providing budgeting assistance. Students, regardless of current aid status, can access financial counseling. OFA manages applications for grants, loans, and Work-Study employment, primarily awarded based on financial need.

EMERGENCY FINANCIAL ASSISTANCE

The University of Michigan offers several types of assistance for students experiencing an emergency situation or one-time, unusual, unforeseen expense while in school. Options include grants and short-term, interest-free loans.

Situations that warrant funding may include:

- Medical, dental or mental health emergencies for the student
- Major accidents and events such as fire and natural disasters
- Expenses related to the death of an immediate family member

Dissemination Plan

IHPI offers its members a broad array of communication vehicles and support services to disseminate research findings to external and internal stakeholders. These vehicles and services include:

Consulting with members

on communications options for their research, both when they first publish results and when past work becomes timely because of new policy developments.

Disseminating the work of IHPI members & teams via traditional and new media channels and **connecting with reporters**, in concert with other U-M media relations professionals.

Highlighting research

through news and feature stories, and robust profiles of [each IHPI member](#).

Publishing

the [IHPI Informs](#) external newsletter which is distributed to reporters, policymakers, associations and professional societies, and think tanks, among others.

Sharing IHPI members' work & institute news via [Twitter](#) & [LinkedIn](#)

Strategizing to share IHPI briefs

that present bodies of research findings to lay audiences.

Helping members strategize op-eds

and articles for [The Conversation](#) and other widely read media outlets.

Reviewing visual abstracts

prepared by members to help them convey key research findings.

Other helpful links (U-M Level 1 Login Required)

Read our member newsletter [IHPI Connect](#)

Nominate a member for an [IHPI Policy Impact Award](#)

Work with the [Policy Engagement & External Relations Team](#)

Find out about making [Sponsorship Requests](#) for events and initiatives

The Six Capitals

INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL

HUMAN CAPITAL

NATURAL CAPITAL

PRODUCTIVE CAPITAL

SOCIAL CAPITAL

FINANCIAL CAPITAL

Intellectual Capital

University of Michigan Technology Transfer Policy

The majority of UOM intellectual property comes from students (as assignments)/researchers/employees innovation. In order to set rules and legally protect the institution, the school has a policy on the matter (as of Oct. 2023); here is a few citations from the official document:

[...]

II. OWNERSHIP OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

- *Intellectual Property made (e.g., conceived or first reduced to practice) by any person, regardless of employment status, with the direct or indirect support of funds administered by the University (regardless of the source of such funds) shall be the property of the University, except as provided by this or other University policy. [...]*

This policy also cites another document entitled "**Ownership of Copyrighted Works Created At or In Affiliation With the University of Michigan With the University of Michigan**" which is used as the University's copyright ownership policy. the following is stated (as of Oct. 2023):

[...]

- **The Default:** *Under U.S. copyright law, the University holds the copyright (as "works made for hire") in copyrighted works authored by its EMPLOYEES who are acting within the scope of their employment. Otherwise, the University does not hold copyright in a work, unless the copyright has been transferred legally to it by written assignment or other process of law.*
- **Transfer of SCHOLARLY WORKS:** *In light of the default, the University, hereby, transfers any copyright it holds in SCHOLARLY WORKS to the FACULTY who authored those works [...]*

Human Capital

Here are some statistics:

Number of Employees:
35,000

Average Salary:
\$51,761 per year

Employees education:

- The most common highest **degree** level of University of Michigan employees is bachelors, with 64% of employees having at least a bachelors.
- The most common **major** among University of Michigan employees is psychology. 10% of University of Michigan employees majored in psychology.

Employees' Certifications:

- The most common certification among University of Michigan employees is medical assistant.
- 22% of employees at University of Michigan have a medical assistant.

Average length of employment:

- A plurality of employees at University of Michigan stay for 1-2 years. 28% of University of Michigan employees stay at the company for 1-2 years.
 - It's rare for an employee to stay with University of Michigan for 8-10 years. Only 6% of University of Michigan employees stay at the company for 8-10 years.
-

Natural Capital

Field Properties

HARPER PRESERVE

City: Argentine Township

Property Size: 375 acres

Open to Public?: No

Current Uses: Educational Use

NEWCOMB TRACT

City: Webster Township

Property Size: 247 acres

Open to Public?: No

Current Uses:

- Educational Use
- Research Use
- Public Use & Outreach Activities

Field Properties

RINGWOOD FOREST

City: St. Charles

Property Size: 160 acres

Open to Public?: Yes

Current Uses:

- Research Use
- Current Public Use & Outreach Activities

SAGINAW FOREST

City: Scio Township

Property Size: 80 acres

Open to Public?: Yes

Current Uses:

- Educational Use
- Research Use
- Recreational Use

Field Properties

ST. PIERRE WETLAND

City: Hamburg Township

Property Size: 130 acres

Open to Public?: No

Current Uses:

- Educational Use
- Research Use
- Public Use & Outreach Activities

STINCHFIELD WOODS

City: Dexter Township

Property Size: 777 acres

Open to Public?: Yes

Current Uses:

- Educational Use
- Research Use
- Public Use & Outreach Activities

Productive/Financial Capital

(in thousands)	2022	2021
Assets		
Current Assets:		
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 2,951,905	\$ 1,003,846
Investments for operating activities	1,691,019	1,912,859
Investments for capital activities	559,411	627,926
Investments for student loan activities	68,387	70,481
Accounts receivable, net	996,475	970,600
Current portion of notes and pledges receivable, net	108,164	108,789
Current portion of other assets	179,403	183,656
Cash collateral held by agent	23,037	20,040
Total Current Assets	6,577,801	4,898,197
Noncurrent Assets:		
Unexpended bond proceeds	305,452	52,451
Endowment, life income and other investments	17,837,664	17,532,653
Notes and pledges receivable, net	273,986	260,756
Other assets	126,435	131,951
Capital assets, net	6,265,812	6,432,423
Total Noncurrent Assets	24,809,349	24,410,234
Total Assets	31,387,150	29,308,431

Interestingly enough, the UOM does prefer liquidity over material/technological assets as stated in the university's 2022 *Annual Report* (pg. 30):

[...]

Current assets consist primarily of cash and cash equivalents, operating and capital investments, and accounts receivable and increased \$1.7 billion to \$6.6 billion at June 30, 2022, as compared to \$4.9 billion at June 30, 2021, primarily as a result of the University's continued focus on liquidity. [...]

However we know for sure that the institution owns at least 6 field properties (view pages above) on top of 3 highly modern and equipped facilities used as campuses: Ann Arbor, Dearborn and Flint.

Social Capital

Innovation Partnerships, investors

The university's ventures team maintains connections with investors around the country and the world to accelerate the growth of startups.

Accelerate Blue Fund (ABF)

The Accelerate Blue Fund is an early-stage venture fund that invests exclusively in University of Michigan licensed startups. The goal of Accelerate Blue is to bridge the funding gap between initial launch and angel/venture capital funding for startups based on University of Michigan intellectual property. Here are a few honourable mentions from the startup portfolio:

The logo for Movellus, consisting of the word "MOVELLUS" in white, uppercase letters on a black rectangular background.

The logo for CubeWorks, featuring a stylized blue and orange cube icon followed by the word "CubeWorks" in blue, lowercase letters.

Corporate Sponsored Research

The school's Corporate Research Alliances team is available to assist faculty exploring corporate sponsored research relationships at any stage in the process, from early ideation, licensing, and business terms through agreement execution with the support of the following research alliances:

Sources:

- https://spg.umich.edu/sites/default/files/policies/303x04_4.pdf
- <https://spg.umich.edu/sites/default/files/601x28.pdf>
- <https://www.zippia.com/university-of-michigan-careers-1417525/demographics/#>
- <https://seas.umich.edu/about/facilities-locations/field-properties>
- https://2022.annualreport.umich.edu/uploads/fy_2022_annual_report_final_web.pdf
- <https://innovationpartnerships.umich.edu/investors/>

Sources:

- <https://umich.edu/facts-figures/>
- <https://umich.edu/about/>
- <https://www.usnews.com/best-colleges/university-of-michigan-ann-arbor-9092#:~:text=It%20has%20a%20total%20undergraduate,is%20National%20%20Universities%2C%20%2321.>
- <https://www.usnews.com/education/best-global-universities/university-of-michigan-170976#uniData>
- <https://www.zippia.com/university-of-michigan-careers-1417525/demographics/>
- <https://regents.umich.edu>
- <https://regents.umich.edu/regents/>
- <https://it.umich.edu/governance>
- <https://it.umich.edu/community>
- <https://2022.annualreport.umich.edu/uploads/fy22-complete-financial-statements.pdf>
- https://obp.umich.edu/wpcontent/uploads/pubdata/budget/ubudgetbook_fy24.pdf
- <https://sph.umich.edu/community/student-experience/campus-resources.html>
- <https://provost.umich.edu/resources-policies/student-resources/emergency-funds/>
- <https://ihpi.umich.edu/members/communications-dissemination>
- <https://umich.edu/>
- <https://www.collegetuitioncompare.com/edu/170976/university-of-michigan-ann-arbor/enrollment/#gender-block-2022-2023>

Paper Methodology

Resources:

- Personal knowledge (one team member has had experience with the university)
- University's official website
- Articles (view sources for more specification)
- Public Documentation
- Public statistics from previous studies

Abbreviations:

UOM = University of Michigan

VPIT-CIO = Vice President for Information Technology & Chief Information Officer.

STAC = Strategic Technology Advisory Committee

IT= Information Technology

CoPs = Communities of Practice

FY= Fiscal year

IPE = Michigan Center for Interprofessional Education

MICHR = Michigan Institute for Clinical and Health Research

SAPAC = Sexual Assault Prevention and Awareness Center

CAPS= Counseling and Psychological Services

OFA = Office of Financial Aid

ABF= Accelerate Blue Fund

UNIVERSITY OF
MICHIGAN

1109 Geddes Ave,
Ann Arbor, MI 48109-
1079

+1 (734) 764-6270

<https://umich.edu/>

info@umich.edu

This work was completed as part of the Public Management course at the SAA, University of Turin, under the supervision of Prof. Valerio Brescia.

The elements presented in this assignment have been developed in accordance with the guidelines defined by Professors Paolo Biancone, Silvana Secinaro, Valerio Brescia, and Davide Calandra.